

1 TITLE:

2 Plasma miR-134-5p: A Candidate Biomarker For Predicting Non-Response To Anti-TNF
3 Therapy In Rheumatoid Arthritis

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27 ABSTRACT

28 Tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (anti-TNF agents) are a milestone in rheumatoid
29 arthritis (RA) management, although 20-40% of RA patients do not achieve clinical
30 remission. Identifying reliable biomarkers to predict the therapeutic response to anti-TNF
31 agents remains an unmet clinical need. This study aimed to identify and validate plasma
32 microRNAs (miRNAs) as biomarkers of response to anti-TNF treatment. A two-stage
33 prospective observational (discovery and validation) study was performed. The study
34 population comprised anti-TNF-naïve RA patients and sex- and age-matched healthy
35 controls (HC). Whole miRNA expression was assessed using the Illumina NextSeq 550
36 platform, followed by bioinformatic analysis. Differentially expressed miRNAs identified
37 in the discovery phase were quantified using real-time quantitative PCR in the validation
38 cohort. Logistic regression analysis assessed associations between miRNA expression
39 and response to anti-TNF treatment. A total of 94 participants were included: 70 anti-
40 TNF-naïve RA patients (discovery $n = 28$; validation $n = 42$) and 24 healthy controls (14
41 and 10, respectively). Clinical response at week 24 was defined as DAS28-CRP < 3.2
42 (responders) versus DAS28-CRP ≥ 3.2 (non-responders). Non-responders were
43 characterised by higher inflammatory activity, poorer HAQ scores, and a higher
44 prevalence of smoking. Forty-five miRNAs were differentially expressed between RA
45 patients and HC, and 9 were expressed between responders and non-responders ($p <$
46 0.05). In the validation cohort, miR-134-5p differed between responders and non-
47 responders ($\Delta C_{t\text{Responders}} = 4.088(\pm 1.266)$; $\Delta C_{t\text{Non-Responders}} = 5.640(\pm 2.872)$;
48 $\Delta\Delta C_{t\text{RespondersVsNon-Responders}} = -1.552$; Fold-Change = 2.932; $p = 0.024$). Logistic regression
49 adjusted for age and sex showed higher miR-134-5p expression to be associated with lack
50 of response to anti-TNF therapy (OR, 1.74; 95% CI: 1.02–2.93; $p = 0.039$). In conclusion,
51 miR-134-5p may serve as a predictive biomarker of poor response to anti-TNF therapy
52 in RA.

53 KEYWORDS

54 anti-TNF; biomarker; miRNA, rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory activity

55

56 INTRODUCTION

57 Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disease characterised by persistent
58 synovial inflammation, progressive joint damage, and functional disability (1). It has been
59 estimated that RA affects 0.5-1% of the global population, with a marked female
60 predominance (2). Despite extensive research, the molecular mechanisms underlying
61 clinical heterogeneity, inflammatory activity, and response to treatment in RA patients
62 remain unclear (3).

63 Current RA therapy comprises both synthetic and biologic disease modifying anti-
64 rheumatic drugs (DMARDs). Tumour necrosis factor inhibitors (anti-TNF) in particular
65 have advanced the management of RA by markedly improving prognosis and quality of
66 life (4). However, 20-40% of RA patients treated with biological DMARDs do not
67 achieve an adequate response owing to lack of efficacy, adverse events, or loss of response
68 during treatment (5). Consequently, it is necessary to identify biomarkers that predict
69 response to treatment and enable rheumatologists to select optimal therapy, avoid
70 toxicities, and reduce healthcare costs.

71 MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small (20-22 nucleotides long), highly conserved,
72 endogenous non-coding RNA molecules. They post-transcriptionally regulate gene
73 expression by binding to complementary sequences in the 3'-untranslated regions of target
74 mRNAs (6). miRNAs are thought to regulate more than 60% of the protein-coding genes
75 (7). Therefore, they play a key role in numerous biological processes such as immune
76 activation, cell differentiation, and cytokine signalling. In recent years, miRNAs have
77 emerged as promising diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in autoimmune
78 inflammatory diseases, including RA (8).

79 The literature shows that RA patients have altered miRNA expression profiles in blood,
80 plasma, serum, and synovial fluid samples (9). Furthermore, specific miRNAs (miR-
81 146a, miR-155, miR-223, and miR-125b) have been associated with severity of RA and
82 response to DMARDs (10). However, the findings of most published articles are restricted
83 by methodological limitations, small sample size, and marked heterogeneity between
84 cohorts, thus complicating the validation of miRNA profiles as reproducible clinical
85 biomarkers (8). Several studies have evaluated circulating miRNAs as predictors of anti-
86 TNF effectiveness in RA, supporting their potential clinical utility but also highlighting

87 important barriers to reproducibility. Reported signals and effect sizes have often varied
88 across cohorts, likely due to differences in biospecimen type (serum vs plasma vs PBMC),
89 pre-analytics (including hemolysis), profiling platforms (RT-qPCR vs NGS),
90 normalization strategies, and response definitions at follow-up. More recent integrative
91 approaches combining broader miRNome profiling with multivariable models and
92 ROC/AUC-based evaluation suggest that predictive performance may improve when
93 miRNAs are considered within clinical-molecular panels rather than as single markers
94 (8,11–13). These observations underscore the need for prospective studies with a
95 discovery-validation structure and clearly defined endpoints to identify robust baseline
96 circulating predictors of anti-TNF response.

97 Rheumatoid arthritis is clinically heterogeneous, and inter-individual differences in
98 inflammatory pathways may contribute to variability in response to cytokine blockade.
99 Diverse synovial inflammatory programs and incomplete regulation of NF- κ B signaling
100 illustrate mechanistic variability that could plausibly influence therapeutic response (14).
101 Genomic studies also support a shared autoimmune architecture, implicating immune
102 regulatory loci that may shape baseline immune set points and treatment outcomes (15).
103 Heterogeneity is further evident in treatment response and toxicity to conventional
104 therapy, including pharmacogenetic variability affecting methotrexate (16). Emerging
105 immunothrombotic and immunometabolic mechanisms reinforce the need for blood-
106 based predictors that integrate systemic biology (17,18). In this context, circulating
107 microRNAs represent attractive candidates, and recent computational approaches for
108 biomarker discovery and panel optimization provide a methodological foundation for
109 developing and evaluating circulating miRNA predictors of anti-TNF response (19–22).

110 Therefore, this study aimed to identify and validate baseline plasma miRNAs associated
111 with clinical response to first anti-TNF therapy at week 24. As an exploratory analysis,
112 we assessed within-patient changes from baseline to week 24 to evaluate potential on-
113 treatment modulation.

114 PATIENTS AND METHODS

115 *Study design*

116 An observational prospective study was conducted. The study population comprised RA
117 patients and sex- and age-matched healthy controls (HC). RA was diagnosed according

118 to the 2010 criteria of the American College of Rheumatology/European League against
119 Rheumatism (ACR/EULAR) classification criteria (23). Participants were consecutively
120 recruited between June 2022 and June 2023 during routine visits to the Rheumatology
121 Department of Hospital Universitario de Málaga, Málaga, Spain. Eligible patients were
122 aged ≥ 16 years, naïve to biological therapy and had been prescribed their first anti-TNF
123 treatment with moderate-to-high disease activity at baseline (28-joint Disease Activity
124 Score [DAS28] ≥ 3.2), despite treatment with conventional synthetic disease-modifying
125 antirheumatic drugs (csDMARDs). Patients with other rheumatic diseases, except
126 secondary Sjögren's syndrome, were excluded. The HC group comprised unrelated
127 individuals from the same geographical area.

128 Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment. Both the
129 study and the protocol fulfilled the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. The study was
130 approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Málaga (“Comité de Ética de la
131 Investigación de Málaga”), with identification code: PI22/01207.

132 All participants underwent clinical and analytical evaluations at two time-points: prior to
133 initiation of anti-TNF treatment (baseline visit, W0) and after 24 weeks of treatment
134 (follow-up, W24). At both time-points, peripheral blood samples were obtained from
135 individuals and were collected in K2-EDTA tubes (#12977696, Beckton Dickson, NJ,
136 USA). Rapidly, samples were centrifuged at 2000g for 15 min, the plasma was aliquoted
137 in cryotubes (#C3236-50EA, Nunc, Thermo Fisher Scientific, NY, USA) and finally
138 stored at -80 °C until their use.

139 Following published recommendations for RNA-seq studies involving human samples
140 (24,25), the discovery cohort comprised 14 individuals per group at each time-point:
141 responders (n = 14), non-responders (n = 14), and HC (n = 14). An independent validation
142 cohort comprised 52 individuals: 42 RA patients and 10 HC.

143 *Sociodemographic and clinical variables*

144 Demographic, clinical, analytical, and treatment-related data were collected by
145 rheumatologists during routine clinic practice. All data were registered in a secure
146 database following a standardized protocol.

147 Demographic variables included age (years), sex, and ethnic background. Cardiovascular
148 risk variables were recorded. These included smoking (smoker or non-smoker), obesity
149 (body mass index ≥ 30 kg/m²), high blood pressure (defined as $\geq 140/90$ mmHg or
150 ongoing antihypertensive treatment), diabetes mellitus diagnosed according to American
151 Diabetes Association criteria (26), dyslipidaemia (total cholesterol > 200 mg/dL, LDL
152 cholesterol > 160 mg/dL, or triglycerides > 175 mg/dL), and history of cardiovascular
153 disease.

154 For RA patients, the date of symptom onset, date of diagnosis, and disease duration were
155 recorded, as were a series of laboratory parameters: rheumatoid factor (RF) (reference
156 value [RV] 20 U/mL; high titres > 60 U/mL), anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies
157 (ACPA) (RV 10 U/mL; high titres > 340 U/mL), C-reactive protein (CRP, mg/dL), and
158 erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR, mm/h).

159 The cumulative inflammatory burden from diagnosis to W0 was estimated as the mean
160 of all DAS28 values recorded over of the disease course. After 24 weeks of anti-TNF
161 treatment, disease activity was categorized/defined as low-remission (DAS28-CRP < 3.2)
162 or moderate-high (DAS28-CRP ≥ 3.2). Disease severity variables were also documented,
163 including the presence of radiographic erosions and physical disability, assessed based on
164 the mean score on the Spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ)
165 (27) during the course of the disease.

166 Concomitant treatment with csDMARDs (methotrexate, leflunomide, sulfasalazine, or
167 hydroxychloroquine) and glucocorticoids, including the dose administered at each visit,
168 was also recorded.

169 *miRNA expression*

170 Total plasma miRNA was isolated using the RNeasy Serum/Plasma Advanced Kit
171 (#217204, Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) following the manufacturer's instructions. 10 pM
172 of cel-miR-39-3p spike-in or exogenous control (Assay 478293_mir, #10620310, Thermo
173 Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) was added to each sample to monitor extraction
174 efficiency. Then, purity and quality were evaluated using the NanoPhotometer™
175 spectrophotometer (IMPLEN, CA, USA), the concentration was determined using the
176 Qubit RNA Assay Kit (#Q32852, Invitrogen, MA, USA) with the Qubit 3.0 fluorometer
177 (Invitrogen), and the integrity of the concentration was assessed using the RNA Nano

178 6000 Assay Kit (#5067-1511, Agilent Technologies, CA, USA) with the Agilent 2100
179 Bionalyzer system (Agilent Technologies).

180 For the discovery phase, prior to miRNA-seq, 1 μ g of total RNA sample was spent to
181 prepare small RNA libraries using the NEBNext[®] Multiplex Small RNA Library Prep Set
182 for Illumina[®] (#E7560S, New England Biolabs, MA, USA) following the manufacturer's
183 protocol. Libraries were then pooled and sequenced on the Illumina NextSeq 550
184 platform (Illumina, CA, USA), generating 75-bp single-end (SE) reads with a minimum
185 depth of 5-10 million reads per sample.

186 Once miRNA-seq results were analysed, differential miRNA expression profiles between
187 groups of individuals were identified. In order to select the miRNAs for the validation
188 study, the combined criteria of statistical significance, magnitude of the change in
189 expression, and biological relevance were applied (11). First, miRNAs were ranked based
190 on the adjusted significance value obtained in comparisons between the different groups.
191 Next, a fold change threshold was established: ≥ 2 for over-expressed miRNAs and ≤ 0.5
192 for under-expressed miRNAs. Finally, miRNAs whose target genes were involved in
193 biological functions related to the pathophysiology of RA and response to treatment,
194 according to the available literature, were prioritised. The selected housekeeping miRNAs
195 were hsa-miR-3184-5p, hsa-miR-128-3p, and hsa-let-7d-3p.

196 The expression of the miRNAs identified as candidates in the discovery phase was
197 assessed using quantitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with specific probes for
198 each miRNA. Reverse transcription of miRNA was performed with a TaqMan Advanced
199 miRNA cDNA Synthesis Kit (#A28007, Thermo Fisher Scientific) using 2 μ L of isolated
200 miRNA, according to the manufacturer's protocol, on a C1000 Touch PCR thermal cycler
201 (BioRad, Hamburg, Germany). The relative expression of miRNA in serum/plasma was
202 determined with TaqMan microRNA assays (S. Table 1). RT-qPCR was performed on a
203 Quant Studio 12K instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using TaqMan Fast Advanced
204 Master Mix (#4444557, Thermo Fisher Scientific) following the manufacturer's protocol.
205 The reaction was performed in triplicate under the following conditions: 95°C for 20 s,
206 40 \times 1 s at 95°C, and 20 s at 60°C. The same RT-qPCR protocol was followed for the
207 exogenous control and markers of haemolysis. The relative expression of each candidate
208 miRNA was calculated by delta delta Ct method (28), following MIQE guidelines (29).
209 Briefly, the mean Ct value of the 3 endogenous miRNAs (miR-3184-5p, miR-128-3p, and

210 let-7d-3p) was calculated to obtain the delta Ct of each candidate miRNA ($\Delta Ct = Ct$
 211 endogenous – Ct target). Then, the delta delta Ct was assessed as $\Delta\Delta Ct = \Delta Ct$ group A –
 212 ΔCt group B. Finally, the fold change was calculated (Fold-change = $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$).

S. Table 1. TaqMan probe used for each miRNA

Assay ID	Assay Name	Sequence
478412_mir	hsa-miR-106b-5p	UAAAGUGCUGACAGUGCAGAU
477827_mir	hsa-miR-92a-3p	UAUUGCACUUGUCCCGGCCUGU
477983_mir	hsa-miR-223-3p	UGUCAGUUUGUCAAAUACCCCA
478107_mir	hsa-miR-451a	AAACCGUUACCAUUACUGAGUU
477860_mir	hsa-miR-16-5p	UAGCAGCACGUAAAUAUUGGCG
477910_mir	hsa-miR-142-3p	UGUAGUGUUUCCUACUUUAUGGA
477901_mir	hsa-miR-134-5p	UGUGACUGGUUGACCAGAGGGG
478817_mir	hsa-miR-3184-5p	UGAGGGGCCUCAGACCGAGCUUUU
477892_mir	hsa-miR-128-3p	UCACAGUGAACCGGUCUCUUU
477848_mir	hsa-let-7d-3p	CUAUACGACCUGCGCCUUUCU

miRNAs considered endogenous are in bold.

213 *Markers of haemolysis*

214 Because haemolysis can release erythrocyte-derived miRNAs that markedly alter
 215 circulating miRNA profiles in both serum and plasma samples, its presence was
 216 systematically evaluated. Among the different methods for assessing haemolysis, the
 217 relationship between hsa-miR-451a and hsa-miR-23a-3p is the most sensitive for
 218 detecting haemolysis levels as low as 0.001% in serum. Therefore, this approach was
 219 selected and performed as previously described (30). Haemolysis was assessed using the
 220 ΔCq approach based on miR-23a-3p and miR-451a ($\Delta Cq = Cq(\text{miR-23a-3p}) - Cq(\text{miR-}$
 221 $451a)$), applying published thresholds (<5 low, 5–7 moderate, >7 high). Samples
 222 exceeding $\Delta Cq > 7$ were prespecified for exclusion, and ΔCq distributions were compared
 223 across study groups.

224 *Bioinformatic analysis*

225 A standardized bioinformatic pipeline was employed for the analysis of miRNA-seq
 226 results. Quality control of raw single-end reads was performed using FastQC (v0.12.0).

227 Adapter trimming and removal of low-quality reads were carried out with fastp
228 (v1.0.1.16), and post-filtering FastQC reports were inspected to confirm the expected
229 small RNA size distribution. Cleaned reads were aligned using Bowtie2 (v2.0.2) in local
230 alignment mode with the very sensitive local preset. Alignments were performed against
231 the human miRNA reference from miRBase (release v22; 1,917 annotated miRNAs), and
232 in parallel against a microbial small RNA database as described above. Bowtie2 default
233 reporting (best alignment per read) was used. Read counts per miRNA were summarized
234 from SAM/BAM files using the Sam2count.py script to generate the miRNA-by-sample
235 count matrix; alignment summaries (uniquely mapped, multi-mapped, and unaligned
236 reads) were retained and reported for transparency. Sequencing depth and alignment
237 performance were assessed across samples (read depth per sample, percentage mapped to
238 miRNAs, and proportions of uniquely mapped, multi-mapped, and unaligned reads), and
239 are reported in Supplementary Table Sx. To evaluate potential technical effects, principal
240 component analysis (PCA) of normalized counts was performed; no clustering consistent
241 with batch effects was observed. Differential miRNA expression between groups was
242 analyzed using DESeq2 with a negative binomial model and Benjamini–Hochberg false
243 discovery rate (FDR) correction. Differentially expressed miRNAs (miDE) were defined
244 as those with adjusted $p < 0.05$ and $|\text{fold change}| \geq 2$.

245

246 *Statistical analysis*

247 A descriptive analysis was performed for all demographic and clinical variables.
248 Categorical variables were expressed as absolute frequencies and percentages, and
249 continuous variables as means (standard deviation, SD) or medians (interquartile range,
250 IQR), as appropriate. Normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

251 Comparisons of clinical, laboratory, and miRNA variables between RA patients and HC,
252 as well as between responders and non-responders, were performed using Pearson's χ^2
253 test or the t test, as appropriate. Discriminative performance of the models was assessed
254 using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves, and the area under the curve (AUC)
255 with 95% confidence intervals (CI) was reported

256 Logistic regression analyses were conducted to identify miRNAs independently
257 associated with a diagnosis of RA and with response to treatment among RA patients. All

258 statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Mac OS, Version 28
259 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

260 RESULTS

261 *Cohort characteristics*

262 The study population comprised 94 participants: 70 RA patients and 24 HCs (Figure 1).
 263 All individuals were allocated to two independent cohorts: a discovery cohort (28 RA, 14
 264 HC) and a validation cohort (42 RA, 10 HC). Table 2 summarizes the epidemiological
 265 and clinical characteristics of both cohorts.

266 No significant differences were found between RA patients and HC in either cohort
 267 regarding demographic variables, including sex ($p = 0.921$), age ($p = 0.893$), ethnicity (p
 268 $= 1.000$), educational level ($p = 0.993$), and body mass index ($p = 0.664$). Among clinical
 269 and comorbidity variables, only smoking status differed significantly, being more
 270 frequent in RA patients ($p = 0.048$).

271 As expected, RA patients had positive RF and ACPA antibody titres and radiographic
 272 erosions, consistent with established disease. Regarding pharmacological treatment, all
 273 RA patients received csDMARDs and glucocorticoids, whereas these medications were
 274 absent in HC.

275 All samples included in circulating miRNA analyses were within the low-haemolysis
 276 range based on ΔCq (miR-23a-3p – miR-451a), and no samples met the prespecified
 277 exclusion criterion ($\Delta Cq > 7$). ΔCq values did not differ between groups (ANOVA $p =$
 278 0.608), indicating no evidence of differential haemolysis.

279

Table 2. Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of the discovery and validation cohorts

Variable	Discovery cohort			Validation cohort		
	RA (n = 28)	HC (n = 14)	<i>p</i> -value	RA (n = 42)	HC (n = 10)	<i>p</i> -value
Epidemiological						
Female sex, n (%)	24 (85.7)	12 (85.7)	1.000	33 (78.6)	8 (80.0)	0.921
Age (in years), mean (SD)*	57.1 (10.4)	57.3 (5.5)	0.944	55.6 (13.4)	56.2 (11.1)	0.893
Caucasian, n (%)	28 (100.0)	14 (100.0)	1.000	42 (100.0)	10 (100.0)	1.000
Educational level			0.657			0.993
Basic education, n (%)	7 (25.0)	5 (35.7)		12 (28.6)	3 (30.0)	
Non-university higher education, n (%)	14 (50.0)	5 (35.7)		21 (50.0)	5 (50.0)	
University education, n (%)	7 (25.0)	4 (28.6)		9 (21.4)	2 (20.0)	
BMI, kg/m ² , mean (SD)	28.0 (4.9)	28.9 (3.9)	0.572	26.9 (3.7)	26.2 (5.6)	0.664
Comorbidities						
Dyslipidaemia, n (%)	6 (21.4)	0 (0.0)	0.061	10 (23.8)	1 (10.0)	0.337
Hypertension, n (%)	7 (25.0)	2 (14.3)	0.425	11 (26.2)	4 (40.0)	0.386
Smoking habit			0.081			0.048
Non-smoking, n (%)	20 (71.4)	12 (85.7)		32 (76.2)	9 (90.0)	
Smoking, n (%)	8 (28.6)	2 (14.3)		10 (23.8)	1 (10.0)	

Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	4 (14.3)	2 (14.3)	1.000	4 (9.5)	0 (0.0)	0.310
Obesity, n (%)	13 (46.4)	4 (28.6)	0.266	7 (16.7)	2 (20.0)	0.802
Clinical						
Disease duration, months, median (IQR)	54.1 (126.6)	-	-	85.8 (161.5)	-	-
Diagnostic delay, months, median (IQR)	7.4 (9.0)	-	-	5.4 (6.8)	-	-
Erosions, n (%)	14 (50.0)	0 (0.0)	0.001	20 (47.6)	0 (0.0)	0.005
RF+ (> 10 U/mL), n (%)	26 (92.9)	0 (0.0)	<0.001	34 (81.0)	0 (0.0)	<0.001
ACPA+ (> 20 U/mL), n (%)	23 (82.1)	0 (0.0)	<0.001	33 (78.6)	0 (0.0)	<0.001
ACPA > 340 U/mL, n (%)	10 (35.7)	0 (0.0)	0.010	10 (23.8)	0 (0.0)	0.086
DAS28-CRP at baseline, mean (SD)	5.1 (0.9)	-	-	4.7 (0.9)	-	-
DAS28-CRP, average, mean (SD)	3.7 (0.9)	-	-	3.5 (0.8)	-	-
HAQ, median (IQR)	1.5 (0.7)	-	-	1.2 (0.7)	-	-
HAQ, average, mean (SD)	1.1 (0.5)	-	-	1.1 (0.6)	-	-
Treatment						
Methotrexate, n (%)	20 (71.4)	0 (0.0)	<0.001	25 (59.5)	0 (0.0)	<0.001
Hydroxychloroquine, n (%)	4 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	0.137	7 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	0.165
Leflunomide, n (%)	4 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	0.137	7 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	0.165
Sulfasalazine, n (%)	3 (10.7)	0 (0.0)	0.204	16 (38.1)	0 (0.0)	0.019
Glucocorticoids, n (%)	21 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	<0.001	31 (73.8)	0 (0.0)	<0.001
Glucocorticoids, median (IQR)	7.5 (3.8)	-	-	5.0 (2.5)	-	-

Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; HC: healthy controls; SD: standard deviation; BMI: body mass index; IQR: interquartile range; RF: rheumatoid factor; ACPA: anti-citrullinated peptide antibody; DAS28: 28-joint Disease Activity Score; CRP: C-reactive protein; HAQ: Health Assessment Questionnaire.

280 After 24 weeks of anti-TNF therapy, RA patients were classified as responders (DAS28-
281 CRP < 3.2) or non-responders (DAS28-CRP ≥ 3.2). As expected, non-responders had
282 higher cumulative mean (SD) DAS28-CRP scores than responders in both cohorts
283 (discovery cohort, 4.1 [1.0] vs 3.3 [0.5], $p = 0.024$; validation cohort, 4.1 [0.6] vs 3.2
284 [0.7], $p = 0.004$), consistent with more persistent disease activity (Table 3).

285 In the validation cohort, non-responders also had higher mean (SD) HAQ scores than
286 responders (1.4 [0.4] vs 0.9 [0.6], $p = 0.031$), reflecting poorer physical function. In the
287 discovery cohort, the proportion of ACPA-positive patients was significantly lower
288 among non-responders than responders (64.3% vs 100.0%, $p = 0.014$). Additionally, in
289 the validation cohort, smoking prevalence was significantly higher among non-
290 responders than responders (76.9% vs 44.8%, $p = 0.016$).

291

Table 3. Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of responders and non-responders

Variable	Discovery cohort			Validation cohort		
	Responders (n = 14)	Non- responders (n = 14)	<i>p</i> -value	Responders (n = 29)	Non- responders (n = 13)	<i>p</i> -value
Epidemiological						
Female sex, n (%)	12 (85.7)	12 (85.7)	1.000	24 (82.8)	9 (69.2)	0.323
Age (in years), mean (SD)	56.1 (10.6)	58.1 (10.5)		55.6 (12.3)	55.6 (16.0)	0.996
Caucasian, n (%)	14 (100.0)	14 (100.0)	1.000	29 (100.0)	13 (100.0)	1.000
Educational level			0.867			0.600
Basic education, n (%)	4 (28.6)	3 (21.4)		16 (55.2)	3 (23.1)	
Non-university higher education, n (%)	7 (50.0)	7 (50.0)		5 (17.2)	8 (61.5)	
University education, n (%)	3 (21.4)	4 (28.6)		8 (27.6)	2 (15.4)	
BMI, kg/m ² , mean (SD)	29.1 (4.8)	27.0 (4.9)		27.0 (4.0)	26.5 (3.2)	0.683

Comorbidities						
Dyslipidaemia, n (%)	3 (21.4)	3 (21.4)	1.000	6 (20.7)	4 (30.8)	0.478
Hypertension, n (%)	4 (28.6)	3 (21.4)	0.663	8 (27.6)	3 (23.1)	0.759
Smoking habit			0.352			0.016
Non-smoking, n (%)	11 (78.6)	9 (64.3)		16 (55.2)	3 (23.1)	
Smoking, n (%)	3 (21.4)	5 (35.7)		13 (44.8)	10 (76.9)	
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	2 (14.3)	2 (14.3)	1.000	3 (10.3)	1 (7.7)	0.787
Obesity, n (%)	7 (50.0)	5 (35.7)	0.659	5 (17.2)	2 (15.4)	0.881
Clinical						
Disease duration, months, median (IQR)	59.3 (100.4)	53.2 (173.5)	0.734	83.2 (138.5)	83.6 (215.7)	0.155
Diagnostic delay, months, median (IQR)	6.8 (8.7)	10.1 (11.5)	0.125	5.7 (5.9)	7.0 (11.4)	0.629
Erosions, n (%)	7 (50.0)	7 (50.0)	1.000	12 (41.4)	8 (61.5)	0.227
RF+ (> 10 U/mL), n (%)	13 (92.9)	13 (92.9)	1.000	23 (79.3)	11 (84.6)	0.686
ACPA+ (> 20 U/mL), n (%)	14 (100.0)	9 (64.3)	0.014	21 (84.0)	9 (75.9)	0.513
ACPA > 340 U/mL, n (%)	5 (35.7)	5 (35.7)	1.000	10 (34.5)	0 (0.0)	0.015
DAS28-CRP at baseline, mean (SD)	5.2 (0.7)	5.4 (1.1)	0.744	4.6 (0.9)	4.9 (1.1)	0.376
DAS28-CRP, average, mean (SD)	3.3 (0.5)	4.1 (1.0)	0.024	3.2 (0.7)	4.1 (0.6)	0.004
HAQ, median (IQR)	1.5 (0.7)	1.3 (0.9)	0.571	1.2 (0.7)	1.5 (0.7)	0.232
HAQ, average, mean (SD)	1.0 (0.6)	1.2 (0.5)	0.487	0.9 (0.6)	1.4 (0.4)	0.031
Treatment						
Methotrexate, n (%)	10 (71.4)	10 (71.4)	1.000	15 (51.7)	10 (76.9)	0.124
Hydroxychloroquine, n (%)	3 (21.4)	1 (7.1)	0.280	6 (20.7)	1 (7.7)	0.296
Leflunomide, n (%)	1 (7.1)	3 (21.4)	0.280	4 (13.8)	3 (23.1)	0.455
Sulfasalazine, n (%)	0 (0.0)	3 (21.4)	0.067	14 (48.3)	2 (15.4)	0.042
Glucocorticoids, n (%)	10 (71.4)	11 (78.6)	0.663	21 (72.4)	10 (76.9)	0.759
Glucocorticoids, median (IQR)	6.2 (2.5)	7.5 (5.0)	0.605	5.0 (2.5)	5.0 (1.3)	0.983

Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; SD: standard deviation; BMI: body mass index; IQR: interquartile range; RF: rheumatoid factor; ACPA: anti-citrullinated peptide antibody; DAS28: 28-joint Disease Activity Score; CRP: C-reactive protein; HAQ: Health Assessment Questionnaire.

292 *miRNA-seq analysis*

293 Across all small RNA-seq libraries, total read depth ranged from ~1M to >20M reads per
294 sample, with miRNA mapping rates between ~1.9% and ~22.3%. The distribution of
295 uniquely mapped, multi-mapped, and unaligned reads per sample is summarized in S.
296 Table 2, and no systematic differences in mapping efficiency were observed between
297 experimental groups. Principal component analysis (PCA) of normalized miRNA counts
298 (PC1 = 12% and PC2 = 9% variance explained) did not show clustering consistent with
299 technical effects (S. Figure 1), supporting that downstream differential expression results
300 are unlikely to be driven by upstream processing variability.

301 S. table 2: Bowtie2 result

Sample	SE mapped uniquely	SE multimapped	SE not aligned
Control_rep10_bowtie	609956	652941	10561144
Control_rep11_bowtie	775412	702483	8043477
Control_rep12_bowtie	639404	719848	6628353
Control_rep14_bowtie	572271	503003	5544401

Control_rep15_bowtie	332859	255126	6020362
Control_rep1_bowtie	842563	801282	10811229
Control_rep2_bowtie	431461	402311	3422258
Control_rep3_bowtie	522156	431332	5369449
Control_rep4_bowtie	880365	970138	11133267
Control_rep5_bowtie	526576	558157	7557588
Control_rep6_bowtie	624350	565459	6419280
Control_rep7_bowtie	560751	701775	7168733
Control_rep8_bowtie	237684	195454	3421122
Control_rep9_bowtie	273690	244377	4261553
NoRes_F_rep1_bowtie	446345	478312	7401829
NoRes_F_rep2_bowtie	443166	357119	6933026
NoRes_F_rep3_bowtie	499973	117617	4666639
NoRes_F_rep4_bowtie	675881	564145	5714798
NoRes_F_rep5_bowtie	1258543	535698	7565831
NoRes_F_rep6_bowtie	777617	758109	8537298
NoRes_F_rep7_bowtie	602152	487180	9181896
NoRes_I_rep1_bowtie	18583	19743	1080739
NoRes_I_rep2_bowtie	411591	431124	4498286
NoRes_I_rep3_bowtie	806919	1458931	7898542
NoRes_I_rep4_bowtie	67367	120588	1747000
NoRes_I_rep5_bowtie	442255	244374	4795093
NoRes_I_rep6_bowtie	466878	307989	5438236
NoRes_I_rep7_bowtie	537651	458210	5388854
Res_F_rep1_bowtie	1198425	1415155	15913899
Res_F_rep2_bowtie	432318	402548	10476430
Res_F_rep3_bowtie	994005	725235	14235208
Res_F_rep4_bowtie	310398	355815	9829269
Res_F_rep5_bowtie	1186878	1505448	10280376
Res_F_rep6_bowtie	473141	255827	5293497
Res_F_rep7_bowtie	270901	178228	4965635
Res_I_rep1_bowtie	1279006	1504330	15174583
Res_I_rep2_bowtie	1337153	1680148	11220142
Res_I_rep3_bowtie	604697	508055	8625876
Res_I_rep4_bowtie	825751	844931	10579443
Res_I_rep5_bowtie	512509	783288	11780329
Res_I_rep6_bowtie	261217	183384	22687518

Res_I_rep7_bowtie	659133	462184	8751529
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302

303 In the discovery cohort, differential expression analysis identified 45 miRNAs that were
304 significantly deregulated between RA patients and HC (Table 4), suggesting their
305 potential role as diagnostic biomarkers in RA. The differentially expressed miRNAs
306 include miRNAs previously related to oxidative stress, rheumatic diseases such as
307 psoriatic arthritis, conditions secondary to RA such as atherosclerosis and cardiovascular
308 risk, inflammatory processes, and B-cell autoreactivity.

Table 4. Differently expressed miRNAs in RA patients compared to HC

miRNA	Expression	Log fold-change	<i>p</i> -value (adjusted)
hsa-miR-379-5p	Elevated	2.187	0.0051
hsa-miR-3184-3p	Elevated	1.200	0.0007
hsa-miR-409-3p	Elevated	1.898	0.0025
hsa-miR-657	Elevated	2.622	0.0136
hsa-miR-493-3p	Elevated	1.785	0.0421
hsa-miR-574-5p	Elevated	1.238	0.0103
hsa-miR-423-5p	Elevated	1.177	0.0008
hsa-miR-378c	Elevated	3.970	0.0008
hsa-miR-320c	Elevated	2.008	0.0005
hsa-miR-7704	Elevated	4.067	0.0288
hsa-miR-134-5p	Elevated	2.245	0.0073
hsa-miR-370-3p	Elevated	2.457	1.71823E-06
hsa-miR-378a-3p	Elevated	1.127	0.0183
hsa-miR-485-5p	Elevated	2.147	0.0117
hsa-miR-4446-3p	Elevated	1.618	0.0137
hsa-miR-433-3p	Elevated	3.593	0.0133
hsa-miR-320a-3p	Elevated	1.220	0.0421
hsa-miR-1307-3p	Elevated	1.733	0.0002
hsa-miR-1908-5p	Elevated	1.737	0.0179
hsa-miR-320b	Elevated	1.990	0.0007
hsa-miR-193b-5p	Elevated	1.758	0.0285
hsa-miR-744-5p	Elevated	1.037	0.0017
hsa-miR-320d	Elevated	1.996	0.0084
hsa-miR-3168	Elevated	4.213	0.0002
hsa-miR-127-3p	Elevated	1.514	0.0109
hsa-miR-193a-5p	Elevated	2.529	1.71823E-06
hsa-miR-142-3p	Elevated	2.603	0.0073
hsa-miR-483-5p	Elevated	4.404	4.0191E-09
hsa-miR-30a-5p	Reduced	-1.760	0.0066
hsa-miR-30e-5p	Reduced	-1.435	0.0051
hsa-miR-26b-5p	Reduced	-1.103	0.0022
hsa-miR-328-3p	Reduced	-1.254	0.0170

hsa-miR-182-5p	Reduced	-1.999	0.0147
hsa-miR-144-3p	Reduced	-2.383	0.0328
hsa-miR-486-3p	Reduced	-1.166	0.0103
hsa-miR-92a-3p	Reduced	-1.148	0.0007
hsa-miR-186-5p	Reduced	-1.536	0.0009
hsa-miR-16-5p	Reduced	-2.103	0.0022
hsa-let-7b-3p	Reduced	-3.145	0.0170
hsa-miR-363-3p	Reduced	-1.852	7.5162E-06
hsa-miR-3173-5p	Reduced	-4.170	0.0325
hsa-miR-20a-5p	Reduced	-3.412	0.0117
hsa-miR-1275	Reduced	-4.002	0.0334
hsa-miR-223-3p	Reduced	-2.861	0.0020
hsa-miR-486-5p	Reduced	-1.094	0.0288

309 Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; miRNA: micro-RNA.

310 Subsequent analyses comparing responder RA patients at W0 and W24 revealed no
311 significant intra-individual differential expression in any miRNA (data not shown).

312 Finally, the comparative analysis between responders and non-responders at W0 revealed
313 9 miRNAs exhibiting significant differences in miRNA expression between the groups
314 (Table 5). These miRNAs represent potential biomarkers associated with response to anti-
315 TNF treatment. Furthermore, the target genes for these miRNAs were *TP73*, *MAPK3*,
316 *MYC*, and *DLX5*. Notably, miR-134-5p was not differentially expressed between
317 responders and non-responders in the discovery miRNA-seq analysis (Table 5); its
318 association with treatment response was observed in the RT-qPCR validation cohort.

319

Table 5. Differentially expressed miRNAs in responders and non-responders

miRNA	Expression	Log fold-change	p-value (adjusted)	Gene (target)
hsa-miR-3184-3p	Reduced	-1.1211	0.0364	Unknown
hsa-miR-423-5p	Reduced	-1.0949	0.0405	Unknown
hsa-miR-378c	Reduced	-4.7019	0.0015	Unknown
hsa-miR-370-3p	Reduced	-1.8704	0.0184	Unknown
hsa-miR-1307-3p	Reduced	-1.4778	0.0405	Unknown
hsa-miR-320b	Reduced	-1.9942	0.0184	<i>DLX5</i> ; <i>MYC</i>
hsa-miR-3168	Reduced	-5.1928	0.0001	Unknown
hsa-miR-193a-5p	Reduced	-2.4260	0.0004	<i>TP73</i>
hsa-miR-483-5p	Reduced	-3.8457	0.0001	<i>MAPK3</i>

320 Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; miRNA: micro-RNA.

321 *Validation of miRNA-seq results by RT-qPCR*

322 In the discovery phase, miRNA-seq analysis revealed differences in expression profiles
 323 between RA patients and HC, as well as between responders and non-responders.
 324 Seven miRNAs were selected for validation based on combined selection criteria
 325 (including statistical significance, fold-change ≥ 2 or ≤ 0.5 , and biological relevance to
 326 pathways implicated in the pathophysiology of RA and the response to anti-TNF therapy).

327 Validation by RT-qPCR showed no significant differences in expression levels of any
 328 miRNA between RA patients and HC (Table 6). Meanwhile, among the selected
 329 candidates, expression of miR-134-5p significantly differ in non-responders compared
 330 with responders ($\Delta\text{Ct}_{\text{Responders}} = 4.088(\pm 1.266)$; $\Delta\text{Ct}_{\text{Non-Responders}} = 5.640(\pm 2.872)$;
 331 $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}_{\text{RespondersVsNon-Responders}} = -1.552$; Fold-Change = 2.932; $p = 0.0246$). ROC analysis of
 332 miR-134-5p showed modest discrimination (AUC = 0.611, 95% CI 0.47–0.74; $p = 0.120$).

Table 6. Results of the analysis for validation of miRNA expression by RT-qPCR

miRNA	RA patients (n = 42)	HC (n = 10)	<i>p</i> -value	Responders (n = 29)	Non-responders (n = 13)	<i>p</i> -value
miR-106b-5p	-0.371 (± 1.468)	-0.234 (± 1.128)	0.785	-0.542 (± 1.576)	-0.068 (± 1.243)	0.339
miR-92a-3p	-4.905 (± 1.284)	-4.957 (± 0.882)	0.905	-5.057 (± 1.424)	-4.634 (± 0.959)	0.328
miR-223-3p	-5.605 (± 1.220)	-5.266 (± 0.833)	0.412	-5.719 (± 1.332)	-5.403 (± 0.991)	0.444
miR-451-a	-5.828 (± 1.904)	-5.966 (± 1.056)	0.827	-5.924 (± 2.076)	-5.657 (± 1.593)	0.679
miR-16-5p	-3.009 (± 1.512)	-3.259 (± 0.781)	0.617	-3.139 (± 1.676)	-2.776 (± 1.170)	0.478
miR-142-3p	0.028 (± 1.635)	0.542 (± 1.636)	0.379	-0.104 (± 1.529)	0.263 (± 1.854)	0.509
miR-134-5p	4.567 (± 2.080)	4.792 (± 1.899)	0.853	4.088 (± 1.266)	5.640 (± 2.872)	0.025

t test results are presented as ΔCt [mean ($\pm\text{SD}$)] for each miRNA. Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; HC: healthy controls; miRNA: micro-RNA

333 A logistic regression model adjusted for age and sex established a significant association
 334 between higher miR-134-5p expression levels and the lack of therapeutic response to anti-
 335 TNF treatment (OR [95%CI], 1.74 [1.02-2.93]; $p = 0.039$) (Table 7).

336 Finally, to address potential confounding due to baseline clinical differences, we repeated
 337 the logistic regression analyses using expanded adjustment sets. Fully adjusted models

338 for all candidate miRNAs are shown in S. Table 3. In these models, miR-134-5p remained
 339 independently associated with non-response after adjustment for age, sex, smoking status,
 340 baseline DAS28-CRP, and baseline glucocorticoid use (adjusted OR 1.641; 95% CI
 341 1.002–2.677; $p = 0.043$). A dedicated model including baseline clinical covariates

Table 7. Results of the study of the association of miRNAs with RA and therapeutic response in a logistic regression model.

miRNA	RA patients vs HC	Responders vs non-responders
miR-106b-5p	$R^2 = 0.010$ OR: 0.965, 95%CI (0.59-1.57) $p = 0.887$	$R^2 = 0.046$ OR: 1.166, 95%CI (0.72-1.87) $p = 0.527$
miR-92a-3p	$R^2 = 0.018$ OR: 1.180, 95%CI (0.62-2.20) $p = 0.609$	$R^2 = 0.043$ OR: 1.184, 95%CI (0.65-2.14) $p = 0.576$
miR-223-3p	$R^2 = 0.015$ OR: 0.895, 95%CI (0.52-1.51) $p = 0.681$	$R^2 = 0.034$ OR: 1.058, 95%CI (0.64-1.73) $p = 0.825$
miR-451-a	$R^2 = 0.017$ OR: 1.099, 95%CI (0.73-1.63) $p = 0.641$	$R^2 = 0.033$ OR: 0.978, 95%CI (0.66-1.43) $p = 0.910$
miR-16-5p	$R^2 = 0.021$ OR: 1.209, 95%CI (0.74-1.97) $p = 0.446$	$R^2 = 0.032$ OR: 1.018, 95%CI (0.64-1.60) $p = 0.939$
miR-142-3p	$R^2 = 0.012$ OR: 0.895, 95%CI (0.63-1.25) $p = 0.522$	$R^2 = 0.043$ OR: 1.096, 95%CI (0.79-1.50) $p = 0.570$
miR-134-5p	$R^2 = 0.011$ OR: 0.885, 95%CI (0.58-1.34) $p = 0.565$	$R^2 = 0.208$ OR: 1.738, 95%CI (1.02-2.93) $p = 0.039^*$

Abbreviations. RA: rheumatoid arthritis; HC: healthy controls; miRNA: micro-RNA. * $p < 0.05$ after including age and sex in the logistic regression model.

342 alongside miR-134-5p is provided in S. Table 4 (Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.256$).

343

344

S. Table 3. Multivariable logistic regression analyses of candidate plasma miRNAs associated with rheumatoid arthritis (RA vs healthy controls) and with anti-TNF response (responders vs non-responders), using expanded adjustment sets.

miRNA	RA patients vs HC	Responders vs non-responders
miR-106b-5p	$R^2 = 0.061$ OR: 0.982, 95%CI (0.65-1.46) $p = 0.931$	$R^2 = 0.074$ OR: 1.110, 95%CI (0.71-1.71) $p = 0.640$
miR-92a-3p	$R^2 = 0.060$ OR: 1.116, 95%CI (0.67-1.85) $p = 0.672$	$R^2 = 0.077$ OR: 1.193, 95%CI (0.62-1.90) $p = 0.753$
miR-223-3p	$R^2 = 0.065$ OR: 0.952, 95%CI (0.61-1.46) $p = 0.822$	$R^2 = 0.076$ OR: 1.039, 95%CI (0.64-1.66) $p = 0.873$
miR-451-a	$R^2 = 0.061$ OR: 1.063, 95%CI (0.98-1.13) $p = 0.562$	$R^2 = 0.074$ OR: 0.942, 95%CI (0.64-1.36) $p = 0.754$
miR-16-5p	$R^2 = 0.067$ OR: 1.123, 95%CI (0.76-1.64) $p = 0.554$	$R^2 = 0.080$ OR: 0.969, 95%CI (0.62-1.50) $p = 0.886$
miR-142-3p	$R^2 = 0.065$ OR: 0.959, 95%CI (0.72-1.27) $p = 0.773$	$R^2 = 0.085$ OR: 1.118, 95%CI (0.82-1.51) $p = 0.471$
miR-134-5p	$R^2 = 0.067$ OR: 0.847, 95%CI (0.59-1.20) $p = 0.351$	$R^2 = 0.256$ OR: 1.641 (1.002-2.677) $p = 0.043^*$

Abbreviations: RA, rheumatoid arthritis; HC, healthy controls; miRNA, microRNA; OR, odds ratio; CI, confidence interval; DAS28-CRP, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints using C-reactive protein. * $p < 0.05$ in the multivariable model. All logistic regression models comparing RA vs healthy controls (HC) were adjusted for age, sex, and smoking status; smoking status was significant in all RA vs HC analyses. Models comparing responders vs non-responders were adjusted for age, sex, smoking status, baseline DAS28-CRP, and baseline glucocorticoid use; smoking status showed a trend toward association in these models ($p < 0.15$) but did not reach conventional statistical significance ($p \geq 0.05$).

347 S. Table 4. *Univariate and multivariable logistic regression of baseline clinical factors*
 348 *and miR-134-5p associated with non-response to anti-TNF therapy in rheumatoid*
 349 *arthritis.*

Responders vs non-responders			
Variable	Univariate OR (95%CI)	Multivariate OR (95%CI)	p- value
Age, years	1.008 (0.968-1.038)		
Female sex	0.681 (0.202-2.293)		
Smoking habit	2.731 (0.984-7.578)		
Average DAS28	1.011 (0.649-1.577)		
Glucocorticoids	1.355 (0.440-4.176)		
miR-134-5p	1.640 (1.003-2.680)	1.641 (1.002-2.677)	0.043

350 * Nagelkerke $R^2=0.256$

351 *Abbreviations: anti-TNF, tumour necrosis factor inhibitor; CI, confidence interval; DAS28, Disease*
 352 *Activity Score in 28 joints; OR, odds ratio; RA, rheumatoid arthritis. DAS28-CRP, Disease Activity Score*
 353 *in 28 joints using C-reactive protein.*

354

355 DISCUSSION

356 Anti-TNF treatment has significantly advanced management of RA, improving affected
357 patients' quality of life and physical condition. However, a high percentage of patients do
358 not achieve clinical remission after anti-TNF treatment. Therefore, it is clear that specific
359 and sensitive biomarkers are needed to predict therapeutic response and optimize
360 treatment selection (31). In this context, miRNAs have been proposed as promising
361 biomarkers owing to their stability in biological fluids and the role played in both
362 immunological and inflammatory processes in RA. Therefore, we present an
363 observational and exploratory study aiming to identify circulating plasma miRNAs as
364 potential novel biomarkers in RA.

365 miRNA-seq was carried out on a discovery cohort in order to identify miRNA signatures
366 when comparing different groups: RA patients vs HCs, and responder vs non-responder
367 RA patients. A 45-miRNA signature was identified as differentially expressed between
368 RA patients and HCs. Previous literature establishes that several of these miRNAs are
369 involved in mechanistic processes and pathways that are important for the development
370 of RA. Specifically, miR-423-5p and miR-320a-3p have been associated with apoptosis,
371 oxidative stress, and cardiovascular disease (32,33), miR-370-3p with oxidative stress
372 (34), miR-30a-5p with promotion of B-cell hyperactivity (35), and miR-142-3p and miR-
373 223-3p with both inflammation and RA (36–38). Furthermore, after comparing
374 responders and non-responders at baseline a miRNA signature with significant
375 differential expression was identified. This points to a putative baseline molecular
376 fingerprint associated with subsequent anti-TNF response. The currently reported target
377 genes for these miRNAs are *TP73*, *MAPK3*, *MYC*, and *DLX5*, which are implicated in
378 pathways central to rheumatoid synovitis and anti-TNF–modulated inflammation. *TP73*
379 is relevant in DNA-damage response and apoptosis (*TP73*) (39,40), and the activation of
380 p73, protein encoded by *TP73* gene, has been proposed as a therapeutic strategy in RA
381 (41). *MAPK3*, also known as *ERK1*, plays a central role in the MAPK/ERK pathway
382 signalling which is related to RA pathogenesis and inflammatory response (42). *MYC*
383 plays an important role in B-cell homeostasis maintenance as a component of the B-cell
384 receptor (43), this homeostasis is dysregulated in RA. *DLX5* has been recently related to
385 inflammation-induced pain in RA patients (44). The longitudinal analysis of responders
386 (pre- and post-therapy) did not reveal significant changes in miRNA expression,
387 suggesting that these circulating miRNAs are not acutely modulated by anti-TNF therapy

388 over 24 weeks but may instead reflect upstream regulatory states that could predispose to
389 therapeutic non-response.

390 In the independent RT-qPCR validation cohort, 7 candidate miRNAs were selected (miR-
391 106b-5p, miR-92a-3p, miR-223-3p, miR-451-a, miR-16-5p, miR-142-3p, and miR-134-
392 5p) based on combined statistical and biological criteria derived from discovery-phase
393 profiling, ensuring both effect size and mechanistic plausibility. No candidate reached
394 statistical significance in the comparison of RA patients and HCs, whereas miR-134-5p
395 was the only miRNA to be differentially expressed between clinical responders
396 ($\Delta C_{t\text{Responders}} = 4.088(\pm 1.266)$; $\Delta C_{t\text{Non-Responders}} = 5.640(\pm 2.872)$; $\Delta\Delta C_{t\text{RespondersVsNon-}}$
397 $\text{Responders} = -1.552$; Fold-Change = 2.932; $p = 0.0246$). Consistently, a logistic regression
398 model adjusted for sex and age showed that higher miR-134-5p expression was associated
399 with lack of clinical response to anti-TNF therapy (OR [95%CI], 1.74 [1.02-2.93]; $p =$
400 0.039). Notably, non-responders also had higher inflammatory activity, worse functional
401 status (HAQ), and greater smoking prevalence, indicating a more adverse phenotype. This
402 pattern underscores the clinical relevance of identifying molecular predictors that can
403 complement conventional risk indicators during selection of biologic therapy.

404 Although miR-134-5p has not been directly linked to RA aetiology in human studies to
405 date, several lines of evidence have linked this miRNA to central processes in
406 inflammatory, autoimmune regulation, and cell-types impaired in RA (45). It has been
407 communicated that miR-134-5p target the KRAS signalling pathway, affecting T-cell
408 activation threshold and enabling responses to autoantigens (46). Evidence supports that
409 miR-134-5p can interface with innate immune signalling as has appeared within
410 exploratory circulating-miRNA panels in autoimmune diseases, such as Sjögren's
411 syndrome or Still's disease. It has been reported the involvement of miR-134-5p in both
412 Sjögren's syndrome with neuropathy and rheumatic heart disease, pointing to broader
413 immunoinflammatory involvement (47,48). Furthermore, Liao *et al.* associated elevated
414 circulating miR-134 (isoform not specified) with disease activity in adult-onset Still's
415 disease, together with activation of TLR3 and downregulation of IL-18BP (49), an axis
416 that could raise free IL-18 and perpetuate systemic inflammation as it is widely known to
417 occur in RA (50). Beyond inflammation and autoimmunity, studies in animal models
418 addressing nociceptive pathways, suggest a potential relevance of miR-134-5p in pain
419 phenotypes (51,52), commonly accompanying RA. Atherosclerosis leading to
420 cardiovascular disease is the main cause of mortality and morbidity in RA patients (53).

421 In atherosclerosis-related cellular models, miR-134 promotes lipid accumulation and
422 macrophage inflammatory responses by inhibiting *ANGPTL4*, thereby augmenting
423 lipoprotein lipase activity and pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion (54).

424 Taken together, these data support biological plausibility for miR-134-5p as a regulator
425 at the interface of innate sensing, cytokine amplification, and myeloid activation,
426 pathways that are associated with response to anti-TNF therapy. Moreover, our results
427 support that circulating miRNA signatures can stratify therapeutic efficacy in RA and
428 other conditions (8,11–13).

429 This study presents several strengths, including its prospective design, two-stage strategy
430 (discovery and validation), the use of standardized biological samples, and the detailed
431 clinical evaluation of the individuals included. Nevertheless, several limitations warrant
432 consideration. First, the sample size may limit the power to detect modest effect sizes and
433 to validate additional miRNA candidates beyond miR-134-5p. To mitigate this, the
434 discovery thresholds combined effect size and biological plausibility, and an independent
435 cohort was used for validation by RT-qPCR. It was possible to identify differences
436 between groups in both cohorts that are in line with the literature, to analyse several
437 miRNAs related to RA, and to validate miR-134-5p as a novel potential biomarker for
438 response to anti-TNF treatment. Still, multicentre replication with larger samples is
439 required to refine estimates and assess robustness across care settings. Furthermore, miR-
440 134-5p was validated in a modest sample; thus, this result should be viewed as hypothesis-
441 generating and requires replication in larger, independent cohorts. Second, as this was a
442 single-centre study, it is difficult to apply the results in the general RA population.
443 Therefore, further multicentre studies would be necessary to confirm the clinical utility
444 of miR-134-5p as biomarker in RA. Third, the discovery RA vs healthy control miRNA-
445 seq signature did not replicate in the RT-qPCR validation for the tested candidates. This
446 may reflect cross-platform differences, cohort heterogeneity, and the limited discovery
447 sample size (with potential effect-size inflation). Although we used standardized pre-
448 analytics, spike-in and haemolysis controls, and reference-miRNA normalization,
449 residual technical variability or batch effects cannot be fully excluded; thus, this
450 diagnostic signature should be considered exploratory and requires replication in larger
451 cohorts. In addition, we did not perform mechanistic in vitro validation of predicted miR-
452 134-5p targets (e.g., TP73, MAPK3) in RA synovial fibroblasts or macrophages; such
453 experiments will be addressed in future work to better connect the biomarker signal with

454 relevant inflammatory pathways (including macrophage polarization). Finally, it is
455 important to note that miRNA profiles are compartment-dependent: plasma reflects an
456 integrated systemic signal, whereas PBMC and synovial samples better capture immune-
457 cell and local joint processes. Therefore, diagnostic signatures described in
458 PBMC/synovium may not fully translate to plasma, and cross-platform differences
459 (miRNA-seq vs RT-qPCR) and dilution effects may contribute to limited replication of
460 RA vs HC findings (55). In this context, while miR-223-3p and miR-142-3p are recurrent
461 in previous RA panels (often reflecting inflammatory/myeloid activity) (36–38), our main
462 validated finding was the baseline association of miR-134-5p with anti-TNF non-
463 response, consistent with a predictive rather than pharmacodynamic marker.

464

465 CONCLUSIONS

466 This two-stage study identified a 45-miRNA RA patients vs HC signature and a 9-miRNA
467 baseline signature associated with response to anti-TNF. miR-134-5p was the only
468 candidate validated by RT-qPCR, independently predicting non-response after
469 adjustment for age and sex, supporting further studies addressing its use in pre-treatment
470 stratification. Target mapping (*TP73*, *MAPK3*, *MYC*, *DLX5*) anchors the signature in
471 apoptosis, MAPK/ERK signalling, and cell-cycle control by TNF. Lack of on-treatment
472 modulation indicates predictive rather than short-term pharmacodynamic behaviour.
473 Overall, our results present miR-134-5p as a promising candidate associated with non-
474 response in RA patients. Nevertheless, larger multicentre studies including more diverse
475 clinical profiles are required to validate our results prior its clinical application, and to
476 elucidate the underlying mechanisms of both the miR-134-5p and the 9-miRNA
477 signatures associated with response to anti-TNF treatment.

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496 AUTHOR’S CONTRIBUTION

497 Design of the study: N.M-V. and A.F.-N. Writing the first draft of the manuscript: A.M.
498 and J.M.L.-M. Laboratory determinations: A.M., J.M.L.-M, P.R.-L., R.B., and D.L-P.
499 Data curation: A.M. and P.R.-L. Patient recruitment and clinical data collection: N.M-V.,
500 S.M-A., A.G-S., F.O-M., and A.F-N. Supervision: N.M.-V. Writing-review and edition:
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502 the published version of the manuscript.

503 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

504 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or
505 financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. A patent
506 application (application number: P202630271, filed February 26, 2026) related to the use
507 of miR-134-5p as a predictive biomarker of non-response to treatment in rheumatoid
508 arthritis patients, as described in this article, has been filed by the University of Málaga
509 and the Andalusian Health Service (Servicio Andaluz de Salud). Arkaitz Mucientes, José
510 Manuel Lisbona-Montañez, Patricia Ruiz-Limón, Sara Manrique-Arija, Aimara García-
511 Studer, Fernando Ortiz-Márquez, Natalia Mena-Vázquez, and Antonio Fernández-Nebro
512 are listed as inventors.

513

514 Figure 1. STROBE flow-chart of patients' recruitment.

515 S. Figure 1: PCA Result

516

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